

Investigation of the Impact of Thermal Scattering Law Data on Deterministic α -eigenvalue Calculation for a Graphite Block

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates the effect of graphite Thermal Neutron Scattering Law (TSL) data for different porosities on nuclear properties. To evaluate this effect, we performed a numerical analysis of the neutron decay constant α for a non-multiplying graphite system. The evaluated nuclear data for graphite were taken from ENDF/B-VIII.1, which includes some TSL datasets for porosities of 0%, 10%, 20%, and 30% (crystalline-graphite, reactor-graphite-10P, reactor-graphite-20P, and reactor-graphite-30P). The multi-group cross section data for each TSL were generated using FRENDY. As the preliminary study for α -experiment for simple graphite system, the deterministic neutron transport code of GENESIS was used to calculate the α -eigenvalue and the energy spectrum of the neutron flux for a small graphite block. For comparison, the α -eigenvalue calculation based on the free-gas model (i.e., without considering TSL data) was also performed. In addition, the neutron leakage effect on the α -eigenvalue calculation was discussed by comparing the numerical result for an infinite graphite system. Consequently, this study quantitatively shows that the α -eigenvalue increases as the porosity of the graphite TSL data increases. Furthermore, the α -eigenvalue based on the free-gas model was significantly larger than that using the TSL data. This effect is caused by the change in the shape of the neutron energy spectrum due to the TSL data.

Keywords: thermal scattering law, graphite, porosity, α -eigenvalue, GENESIS

1. INTRODUCTION

In this study, we investigate the impact of graphite's Thermal Neutron Scattering Law (TSL) data [1] for different porosities on the neutron decay constant α [2,3] using the α -eigenvalue calculation of the deterministic neutron transport code of GENESIS [4].

To design a highly safe High Temperature Gas-cooled Reactor (HTGR), it is essential to accurately and precisely predict core characteristics parameters. In HTGR, the graphite is used as a structural and moderator material [5]. Since the TSL data determines the energy and the angular distribution of scattered neutrons, the TSL data significantly affect the accuracy of the core characteristics parameter, such as the effective neutron multiplication factor k_{eff} [6].

As another neutronics parameter, previous studies have measured the neutron decay constant α for graphite assemblies using the pulsed neutron method [7–14]. Compared with the k_{eff} -eigenvalue, the measurement value of α will be useful to validate a neutronics code with evaluated nuclear data

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because the α value can be measured even for a non-multiplying system (e.g., the graphite block) and can be numerically analyzed based on the time-eigenvalue calculation. In a non-multiplying system, the α -eigenvalue is determined by the average neutron speed and the balance between the neutron production (scattering) and the annihilation (absorption and leakage) during the asymptotic temporal decay of the neutron flux. For small geometries, the α -eigenvalue strongly depends on neutronics parameters such as the macroscopic total and scattering cross sections and the average directional cosine (or the diffusion coefficient) because the leakage effect is significant. Additionally, the thermalization process due to the scattering affects the neutron energy spectrum, thereby indirectly changing the average neutron speed. Consequently, the α -eigenvalue is highly sensitive to the TSL data.

In this study, we perform a preliminary numerical analysis before the α -experiment for a simple system using the graphite block. The recently evaluated nuclear data library, ENDF/B-VIII.1, contains some kinds of TSL data for graphite with different porosities (crystalline-graphite, reactor-graphite-10P, reactor-graphite-20P, and reactor-graphite-30P) [15,16]. The choice of TSL data has an impact on the results of neutronic calculations. However, when considering a complicated system such as a reactor core [17], it is difficult to distinguish the effect of the TSL data from those of other factors, e.g., other nuclear data except the graphite TSL data, the modeling of the calculation geometry, and so on. Therefore, we focus on a non-multiplying system made of graphite only to eliminate other sources of uncertainty. The purpose of this study is to quantitatively evaluate the effect of the different porosity TSL data of the graphite on the α -eigenvalue. As the neutronics calculation code, we utilize the deterministic neutron transport code GENESIS [18] because the recent version of GENESIS has the unique capability of the α -eigenvalue calculation [4] in a non-multiplying system.

The rest of the present paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the numerical theory of the α -eigenvalue in a non-multiplying system is briefly described. Section 3 presents the preliminary numerical results of α -eigenvalue for a simple calculation geometry of the small graphite block. Finally, concluding remarks are summarized in Section 4. Hereafter in this paper, we use the term “ α -eigenvalue” to refer to the numerical result that corresponds to the fundamental mode, and the term “neutron decay constant” to refer to the measurement value that does not necessarily extract only the fundamental mode.

2. NUMERICAL THEORY

2.1. α -eigenvalue Calculation for Non-neutron-multiplication system

In a non-multiplying system like a graphite block, the angular neutron flux ψ is described by the following time-dependent Boltzmann equation:

$$\frac{1}{v(E)} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \psi - \Sigma_t(\mathbf{r}, E) \psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \mathbf{\Omega}, t) + \int_0^\infty dE' \int_{4\pi} d\Omega' \Sigma_s(\mathbf{r}, E' \rightarrow E, \mathbf{\Omega}' \rightarrow \mathbf{\Omega}) \psi(\mathbf{r}, E', \mathbf{\Omega}', t), \quad (1)$$

where Σ_t and Σ_s are the macroscopic total and scattering cross sections, respectively; v is the neutron speed; and other notations have conventional meanings in reactor physics. After enough time has passed since pulsed neutrons were injected into the target system, let us assume that the magnitude of $\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \mathbf{\Omega}, t)$ exponentially decreases according to $e^{-\alpha t}$. Under such an asymptotic situation, $\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \mathbf{\Omega}, t)$ can be expressed by $\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \mathbf{\Omega}) e^{-\alpha t}$, where $\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \mathbf{\Omega})$ correspond to a unique relative shape with respect

to variables \mathbf{r} , E , and $\boldsymbol{\Omega}$. Then, the α -eigenvalue equation in the non-multiplying system can be expressed as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\Omega} \cdot \nabla \psi + \Sigma_t(\mathbf{r}, E)\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) = \frac{\alpha}{v(E)}\psi(\mathbf{r}, E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}) + \int_0^\infty dE' \int_{4\pi} d\boldsymbol{\Omega}' \Sigma_s(\mathbf{r}, E' \rightarrow E, \boldsymbol{\Omega}' \rightarrow \boldsymbol{\Omega})\psi(\mathbf{r}, E', \boldsymbol{\Omega}'), \quad (2)$$

where α corresponds to the decay constant, i.e., the positive sign means the decrease of neutrons.

The GENESIS code is a neutron transport solver based on the deterministic method using the LEAF (Legendre polynomial Expansion of Angular Flux) method [18]. In the recent version of the GENESIS code [4], the α -eigenvalue equation (2) is solved by a numerically stable algorithm using the time-production term [19,20] instead of the α - k search method [21]. Similar to the conventional k -eigenvalue calculation, the angular flux $\psi_{g,n}$ along the characteristics plane is calculated based on the power iteration for the following equation, which is discretized with respect to the energy group g and the solid angle of the neutron flight direction $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_n$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \boldsymbol{\Omega}_n \cdot \nabla \psi_{g,n} + \Sigma_{t,g}(\mathbf{r})\psi_{g,n}(\mathbf{r}) \\ &= \alpha \sum_{l=0}^{NL} \frac{2l+1}{4\pi} \sum_{m=-l}^l \frac{1}{v_g} \phi_{lm,g}(\mathbf{r}) R_{lm}(\boldsymbol{\Omega}_n) + \sum_{l=0}^{NL} \frac{2l+1}{4\pi} \sum_{m=-l}^l \sum_{g'=1}^{NG} \Sigma_{s,l,g' \rightarrow g} \phi_{lm,g'}(\mathbf{r}) R_{lm}(\boldsymbol{\Omega}_n), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\phi_{lm,g}(\mathbf{r}) = \sum_{n=1}^{NN} w_n R_{lm}(\boldsymbol{\Omega}_n) \psi_{g,n}(\mathbf{r}), \quad (4)$$

where $R_{lm}(\boldsymbol{\Omega})$ represents the real spherical harmonics; w_n is the weight of the solid angle quadrature for the direction $\boldsymbol{\Omega}_n$; NG and NN are the total numbers of energy groups and the directions, respectively; and NL is the order of anisotropic source. Compared to the probabilistic method of the α -eigenvalue calculation with a virtual time-production term [19,20], the GENESIS code approximates the virtual time-production term $\frac{\alpha}{v_g}\psi_{g,n}(\mathbf{r})$ by the functional expansion with the real spherical harmonics, i.e., $\alpha \sum_{l=0}^{NL} \frac{2l+1}{4\pi} \sum_{m=-l}^l \frac{1}{v_g} \phi_{lm,g}(\mathbf{r}) R_{lm}(\boldsymbol{\Omega}_n)$ in Eq. (3).

3. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

3.1. Calculation Conditions

This section explains the calculation conditions of the α -eigenvalues using the GENESIS code for a small graphite system. The purpose of this calculation is to clarify the impact of graphite TSL data for different porosities on the α -eigenvalue through deterministic α -eigenvalue calculations using the GENESIS code.

In this preliminary numerical analysis, the size of the graphite block was 5 cm×5 cm×5 cm. By assuming that the mass density of graphite without impurities was 2.3 g·cm⁻³ and the temperature is 296 K, the nuclide densities of ¹²C and ¹³C were calculated based on the natural abundance [22]. Note that the same nuclide densities were used for the α -calculations using the free-gas model or the different TSL data with different porosity, to investigate the impact of the TSL data only.

As evaluated nuclear data, ENDF/B-VIII.1 [15,16] was used, including the Thermal Neutron Scattering Law (TSL) data for crystalline-graphite, reactor-graphite-10P, reactor-graphite-20P, reactor-graphite-

30P, and graphiteSd that corresponds to a special TSL data of crystalline graphite with the distinct (Sd) effect. The FRENDY code (Ver. 2.05.000) [23,24] was used to process these ENDF-6 formatted files to generate the 1203 group KRAMXS formatted macroscopic cross section data. The energy group structure up to 1 eV (i.e., 1–203 groups) was the same as that of the 252-group structure in SCALE [25], but the energy range from 10^{-5} to 1 eV was divided into 1000 groups equally in lethargy units.

The calculation conditions of the GENESIS code were as follows. The spatial meshes in this preliminary study were divided by $10 \times 10 \times 10$ for x, y, z -directions, respectively. In the LEAF method [18], the linear source approximation was used. The ray trace width was 0.1 cm. The total number of azimuthal angles was equally divided by 32 for 2π . The polar angles were divided using the 6th-order Gauss-Legendre quadrature for π . The relative convergence criteria for the α -eigenvalue was 10^{-6} .

To reduce computational costs, the anisotropy of the scattering source was approximated by the P_0 component with the transport corrected cross section $\Sigma_{tr,g}$. The transport corrected cross section was calculated by the out-scatter approximation, in which the sum of P1 scattering cross sections is subtracted from the total cross section. Since the higher P_N components affect the α -eigenvalue via the leakage effect, the further investigation will be conducted in future research.

3.2. Numerical Results

Figure 1 and Table 1 show the calculation results of the neutron energy spectrum and the α -eigenvalue in a 5 cm×5 cm×5 cm graphite system. In Figure 1 and Table 1, the label “free-gas” represents the numerical result based on the free-gas model; “Crystalline” and “Sd” represent the results using TSL data for crystalline graphite (0% porosity) without and with considering the Sd effect, respectively; and “10% Porosity,” “20% Porosity,” and “30% Porosity” represent the results with TSL data for porosities of 10%, 20%, and 30%, respectively.

First, the use of TSL data significantly affects both the neutron energy spectrum and the α -eigenvalue. When TSL is considered, graphite’s atomic arrangement is treated as a regular crystalline structure. As a result, thermal neutrons behave not just as particles but also as waves. When the neutron wavelength is comparable to graphite’s interplanar distance and satisfies Bragg’s law, the coherent elastic scattering by the Bragg diffraction occurs. In Figure 2, the macroscopic scattering cross section for the TSL data shows Bragg edges, which are discontinuities at specific energies. These edges indicate strong neutron scattering by the crystal lattice. Furthermore, near the Bragg edges, the average directional cosine of the scattering angle oscillates rapidly, which means highly anisotropic scattering. The α -eigenvalue is smaller in the results using TSL data. This reason might be caused by the softer neutron energy spectrum due to the complicated scattering process in the TSL data.

On the other hand, the free-gas model ignores the crystal structure; thus, it has no Bragg edges. In this model, the effect of upscattering in the thermal region is stronger, resulting in a harder neutron energy spectrum compared to the TSL cases. This leads to a higher average neutron speed v , and since the α -eigenvalue is proportional to this speed, its value becomes significantly larger. The results of the free-gas model significantly differ from other results using the TSL data, which implies that it does not correctly represent the physical phenomena in the graphite crystal.

Next, we discuss the effects of different TSL data. The α -eigenvalue tends to increase with porosity. This is because the increased porosity distorts the graphite’s crystal structure, which reduces the coherent elastic scattering due to Bragg diffraction. As a result, the harder neutron energy spectrum

results in a larger α -eigenvalue. In the case of the Sd graphite data, the neutron energy spectrum forms a peak at the Bragg cut-off energy. The Sd graphite data include coherent inelastic scattering effects, where neutrons exchange energy with lattice vibrations [6]. Compared to the crystalline data, the harder energy spectrum due to the Sd effect might result in a larger α -eigenvalue.

Figure 3 and Table 2 show the neutron energy spectrum and the α -eigenvalue in an infinite graphite system without neutron leakage. In an infinite system, the neutron energy spectrum has almost the same shape in all cases. As a result, the α -eigenvalue is also the same for all cases. Since the neutron loss in an infinite system occurs only by the neutron capture reaction, the macroscopic capture cross section only affects calculation results for α -eigenvalues. Therefore, the effects of TSL and porosity might be negligibly small, and the neutron energy spectrum forms a Maxwellian distribution that mainly depends on the graphite temperature.

Figure 1. Calculation Results for the Neutron Energy Spectrum (5 cm×5 cm×5 cm Graphite Block).

Table 1 Calculation Results for the α -eigenvalue (5 cm×5 cm×5 cm Graphite Block).

	free-gas	10% Porosity	20% Porosity	30% Porosity	Crystalline	Sd
α -eigenvalue (s ⁻¹)	37296	3595	3734	4002	2886	3315

Figure 2. Macroscopic Scattering Cross Section Σ_s and Average Directional Cosine $\bar{\mu}$

Figure 3. Calculation Results for the Neutron Energy Spectrum (Infinite Graphite System).

Table 2 Calculation Results for the α -eigenvalue (Infinite Graphite System).

	free-gas	10% Porosity	20% Porosity	30% Porosity	Crystalline	Sd
α -eigenvalue (s^{-1})	97	97	97	97	97	97

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study presented the preliminary numerical analysis of the α -eigenvalue using the GENESIS code for the small graphite block. As a result, we clarified that the different kinds of graphite TSL data have an impact on the α -eigenvalue calculation, which implies the measurement value of α for the graphite block may be useful to judge which of the TSL data is appropriate for the neutronics calculation.

One of the future research topics is to calculate the α -eigenvalue with a more rigorous anisotropy treatment for the scattering and the virtual time-production sources using higher P_N components.

Another topic is the validation of α -eigenvalue calculations by GENESIS for α -experiments conducted in previous pulsed neutron studies [7–14].

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